

Supplementary Material for
Scalable Active Metamaterials for Shape-Morphing

Jipeng Cui, Wei “Wayne” Chen

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1 Unit cell design

The geometric configuration of the unit cell is illustrated in Fig. S1a. The unit cell is defined over a rectangular domain $\Omega = [0, W] \times [0, H]$. For simplicity, we consider the square case with $W = H$. The unit cell consists of two components: a closed-loop rigid linkage (CRL), shown in black, and an internal soft infill composed of stacked arc-shaped beams [1, 2].

1.1 Geometric parameterization of the CRL

As shown in Fig. S1a, the CRL is formed by rigid materials. Each rigid bar has a length L and a width L_c . Adjacent bars are connected by a neck-shaped short link of length L_s , whose narrowest section has a width W_h and a length L_h . This geometry localizes bending at the connection and guides deformation to occur in the hinge region. The values or ranges of all parameters are shown in Table S1.

Figure S1: Unit-cell geometry and deformation configuration. **a**, Geometric parameterization of the CRL and its infill structure. **b**, The resulting deformed configuration.

1.2 Geometric parameterization of the soft infill structure

The internal infill consists of eight stacked circular arc beams arranged around the eight hinge centers, with each beam characterized by distinct geometric parameters. Each stacking arc beam i is composed of two materials with different coefficients of thermal expansion, whose thicknesses are denoted by u_1^i and u_2^i , respectively. The outer radius of the inner beam is denoted by r^i . To allow each beam to bend either inward or outward, an additional binary parameter z^i is introduced to indicate the stacking order, where $z^i = 1$ corresponds to material A on top of material B, and $z^i = 0$ indicates the opposite arrangement. Consequently, each stacked arc beam is parameterized by four variables, resulting in a total of 32 geometric parameters for a single unit cell, i.e., $\mathbf{x} = [r^0, u_1^0, u_2^0, z^0, \dots, r^7, u_1^7, u_2^7, z^7]$. The range of parameters is shown in Table S1.

Table S1: Geometric parameters of a unit cell.

Parameter	Value (mm)	Description
L	1.00	Length of the infill region
L_c	0.03	Width of the CRL bar
L_s	0.06	Length of the neck-shaped link
W_h	0.002	Width of the narrowest section of the neck-shaped link
L_h	0.02	Length of the narrowest section of the neck-shaped link
H	1.06	Total height of the unit cell
W	1.06	Total width of the unit cell
r^i	[0.06, 0.08]	Outer radius of the inner beam
u_1^i	[10^{-3} , 0.08]	Thickness of the outer beam
u_2^i	[10^{-3} , 0.08]	Thickness of the inner beam
z^i	{0,1}	Stacking order

Fig. S1b illustrates the deformation configuration of the ideal CRL, in which the bars are connected by perfect hinges. Since all CRL bars have equal length, the deformation configuration can be fully characterized by the variations of the eight internal angles $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta^0, \dots, \theta^7]$.

2 Macroscale design method

2.1 Constrained Laplacian mesh editing

As described in the main text, the objective function in Eq. 2 consists of three weighted terms: the *Laplacian energy* E_L , the *configuration consistency energy* E_S , and the *target matching energy* E_t .

The Laplacian energy is defined as

$$E_L(\mathbf{v}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \mathbf{v}_i - \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \mathbf{v}_j \right\|^2, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where \mathbf{v} is the vectorization of all vertices \mathcal{V} , $\mathbf{v}_i \in \mathcal{V}$ denotes the coordinate of vertex i , n_i is the number of its neighbors, \mathcal{N}_i is the corresponding neighbor set, and $N = |\mathcal{V}|$. This term penalizes the deviation of each vertex from the centroid of its neighbors, thereby preserving mesh topology and promoting smooth deformation. In matrix form, this energy can be written compactly as

$$E_L(\mathbf{v}) = \|\mathbf{L}_L \mathbf{v}\|^2, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where \mathbf{L}_L is the normalized graph Laplacian matrix.

The configuration consistency energy is defined as

$$E_S(\mathbf{v}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^8 \|\mathbf{v}_j^{(i)} - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_j^{(c_i^*)}\|^2, \quad (\text{S3})$$

where $\mathbf{v}_j^{(i)}$ denotes the j -th vertex of cell i , and $\{\hat{\mathbf{v}}_j^{(c_i^*)}\}_{j=1}^8$ is the nearest-neighbor configuration retrieved from \mathcal{D} after alignment:

$$c_i^* = \arg \min_{1 \leq c_i \leq |\mathcal{D}|} \sum_{j=1}^8 \|\mathbf{v}_j^{(i)} - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_j^{(c_i)}\|^2. \quad (\text{S4})$$

This term encourages each unit cell to remain close to a configuration in \mathcal{D} , avoiding out-of-distribution solutions and implicitly constraining mesh edge lengths to remain near their initial values. In matrix form, this energy can be written as

$$E_S(\mathbf{v}) = \|\mathbf{L}_S \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{b}^{\mathcal{D}}\|^2, \quad (\text{S5})$$

where $\mathbf{L}_S = \text{diag}(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_N)$ is a diagonal matrix with d_j denoting the number of unit cells that vertex j participates in, and $\mathbf{b}^{\mathcal{D}}$ is a vector whose j -th entry is the sum of the reference positions of vertex j across the nearest-neighbor configurations of all cells containing it:

$$\mathbf{b}_j^{\mathcal{D}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \hat{\mathbf{v}}_j^{(i)}, \quad (\text{S6})$$

The target matching energy is defined as

$$E_t(\mathbf{v}) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{F}} \|\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_i^t\|^2, \quad (\text{S7})$$

where \mathcal{F} is the set of handle vertices and \mathbf{v}_i^t is the target position of handle vertex i . This term enforces the boundary conditions by driving the vertices with prescribed target positions toward their desired locations. In the matrix form, it could be written as,

$$E_t(\mathbf{v}) = \|\mathbf{L}_t \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{b}^t\|^2, \quad (\text{S8})$$

where $\mathbf{L}_t = \text{diag}(\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_n)$ is a diagonal selection matrix with

$$\delta_j = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \mathbf{v}_j \in \mathcal{V}_{\text{handle}}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (\text{S9})$$

and \mathbf{b}^t is the target position vector whose j -th entry equals the prescribed target position \mathbf{v}_j^t if $\mathbf{v}_j \in \mathcal{V}_{\text{handle}}$ and zero otherwise. This term penalizes the deviation of handle vertices from their prescribed target positions.

Substituting Eqs. S2, S5, and S8 into Eq. 2 of the main text, it can be written in algebraic form as

$$E(\mathbf{v}) = w_L \|\mathbf{L}_L \mathbf{v}\|^2 + w_S \|\mathbf{L}_S \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{b}^D\|^2 + w_t \|\mathbf{L}_t \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{b}^t\|^2. \quad (\text{S10})$$

Since each term is quadratic and all weighting coefficients are positive, the resulting optimization problem admits an analytical solution. By differentiating Eq. S10 with respect to \mathbf{v} , we obtain

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial \mathbf{v}} = (w_L \mathbf{L}_L^T \mathbf{L}_L + w_S \mathbf{L}_S^T \mathbf{L}_S + w_t \mathbf{L}_t^T \mathbf{L}_t) \mathbf{v} - (w_S \mathbf{L}_S^T \mathbf{b}^D + w_t \mathbf{L}_t^T \mathbf{b}^t). \quad (\text{S11})$$

By setting Eq. S11 to zero, a concise linear system is obtained:

$$\mathbf{L}^a \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{b}^a \quad (\text{S12})$$

where

$$\mathbf{L}^a = w_L \mathbf{L}_L^T \mathbf{L}_L + w_S \mathbf{L}_S^T \mathbf{L}_S + w_t \mathbf{L}_t^T \mathbf{L}_t, \quad (\text{S13})$$

and

$$\mathbf{b}^a = w_S \mathbf{L}_S^T \mathbf{b}^D + w_t \mathbf{L}_t^T \mathbf{b}^t. \quad (\text{S14})$$

The solution of this linear system corresponds to the optimum of Eq. 2. A pure Laplacian surface editing [3] run to get the initial design. In general, the closest unit cell retrieved from the dataset changes after each solve of Eq. S12. Therefore, the linear system needs to be solved iteratively until convergence.

2.2 Weight analysis

Adjusting the weights of the three energy terms shifts the emphasis of the optimization. In practice, w_t is set to a relatively large value to ensure that the handle vertices achieve their prescribed displacements. Therefore, the analysis mainly focuses on the relative magnitude of the first two terms. By controlling their ratio $r = w_L/w_S$, we evaluate its influence using two diagnostic metrics. *Configuration dissimilarity* measures the deviation of each unit cell from its nearest neighbor in \mathcal{D} , reflecting the feasibility of the subsequent microscale inverse design. *Area variation* quantifies the magnitude of local deformation within each unit cell, serving as an indicator of realization difficulty (i.e., a large area change may indicate that the deformation is physically unrealizable). The computation of *configuration dissimilarity* is shown in the Method, and *area variation* is defined as

$$\Delta A = A' - A^0, \quad (\text{S15})$$

where $A^0 = 1$ is the initial area of each unit cell. The area of the deformed configuration is computed using the shoelace formula [4]:

$$A' = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^8 |x_i y_{i+1} - x_{i+1} y_i|. \quad (\text{S16})$$

where $(x_i, y_i) = \mathbf{v}_i \in \mathcal{V}_{\text{unit}}$ are the vertex coordinates of the unit cell, with the convention $\mathbf{v}_9 = \mathbf{v}_1$. Configuration dissimilarity quantifies the deviation between an optimized unit cell configuration and its nearest neighbor in the dataset \mathcal{D} , serving as an indicator of whether the configuration is out-of-distribution and thus whether it can be reliably handled by the microscale inverse design method. It is computed as

$$\Delta S = \frac{1}{8} \sum_{j=1}^8 \|\mathbf{v}_j - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_j^*\|, \quad (\text{S17})$$

where \mathbf{v}_j denotes the coordinate of the j th vertex in the deformed configuration, and $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_j^*$ denotes the coordinate of the j th vertex in the most similar configuration from the dataset after alignment with the deformed configuration.

We use the curved beam example to illustrate how the two metrics vary with the weight ratio r (Figs. S2a and c). As r increases, the Laplacian energy term dominates, suppressing extreme deformations in individual unit cells and contracting the tails of the area distribution toward the mean (Fig. S2e). This suppression also reduces the extreme dissimilarity scores, as fewer unit cells are forced into configurations far from the dataset. However, the concurrent reduction in the relative weight of the configuration consistency energy weakens the similarity constraint overall, causing a slight upward shift in the bulk of the dissimilarity distribution.

As the deformed configuration evolves during optimization, the nearest-neighbor configuration retrieved from the dataset, and hence the term $\mathbf{b}^{\mathcal{D}}$ in Eq. S12, is updated accordingly, making the optimization problem itself iteration-dependent. Multiple iterations are therefore required until convergence. The influence of the iteration count is analyzed in Figs. S2b and d. The distributions of area variation and configuration dissimilarity as a function of iteration count are shown in Fig. S2f. Before the first iteration, no consistency constraint is active, and the solution reduces to pure Laplacian mesh editing. The retrieved nearest-neighbor configurations are therefore unreliable, as the current unit cell configurations have not yet been guided toward the feasible region of \mathcal{D} . As iterations proceed, the unit cell configurations progressively approach entries in \mathcal{D} , improving the quality of the retrieved nearest neighbors and allowing the consistency constraint to become increasingly effective. This, in turn, contracts the tails of the area distribution and reduces dissimilarity scores.

Figure S2: Effect of weight ratio r and iteration count on ConLME performance, illustrated using a curved beam example. a, b, Distributions of area variation under varying weight ratios r (a) and iteration counts (b). c, d, Distributions of configuration dissimilarity under varying weight ratios r (c) and iteration counts (d). e, f, Evolution of the area variation distribution and configuration dissimilarity score distribution with increasing r (e) and iteration count (f).

3 Microscale design methods

3.1 Adjustable search method

To determine infill designs consistent with the macroscale solution, the adjustable search (AS) strategy performs microscale inverse design by sequentially retrieving unit cell configurations from the dataset \mathcal{D} . Starting from a fixed unit cell, AS searches \mathcal{D} for the configuration that best matches the target local deformation. The retrieved configuration is then substituted into the global structure, and the corresponding unit cell is added to the handle vertex set, updating the macroscale solution for the remaining free vertices. This procedure repeats until all unit cells have been assigned a configuration.

The search order is determined according to the following principles:

1. Unit cells belonging to the fixed set are prioritized;
2. Among cells with equal fixed status, those with a greater number of vertices already included in the fixed vertex set are prioritized;
3. Among cells satisfying the above conditions equally, those undergoing larger deformations are prioritized.

Specifically, the search begins from the fixed unit cell at the boundary and proceeds outward. When two unit cells have equal priority under the first criterion, the one sharing more vertices with the current handle vertex set is selected first; ties are broken by selecting the cell with larger deformation.

The key advantage of this ordering strategy is that it prioritizes cells whose vertex positions are already well-constrained, ensuring that the macroscale solution is updated with reliable reference points and thereby reducing accumulated error in the remaining free vertices.

The AS algorithm proceeds as follows. Given a mesh $(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, a unit cell dataset \mathcal{D} , and an initial fixed cell set \mathcal{F} — where a fixed cell is defined as any unit cell containing at least one handle vertex — the macroscale deformation is first resolved via ConLME to obtain an initial vertex configuration \mathcal{V}_0 . The search order is then determined according to the principles described above. Candidate cells are traversed sequentially in this order; for each cell, the nearest-neighbor configuration is retrieved from \mathcal{D} and aligned to the current cell location by rotating about the axis defined by the known vertex pair, ensuring consistency with the already-fixed vertices. The retrieved configuration is then substituted into the global structure, its vertices are added to the fixed set, and ConLME is re-solved to update the positions of the remaining free vertices. This process repeats until all unit cells have been assigned a configuration.

Algorithm 1: Adjustable Search (AS)

Input: Unit cell vertices $\mathcal{V} = \bigcup_{k=1}^N \{\mathbf{v}_j^{(k)}\}_{j=1}^8$ where $\{\mathbf{v}_j^{(k)}\}_{j=1}^8$ denotes the configuration of the k -th unit cell, unit cell dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{\mathcal{C}^{(k)}\}_{k=1}^M$ where $\mathcal{C}^{(k)} = \{\hat{\mathbf{v}}_j^{(k)}\}_{j=1}^8$ is one configuration in the dataset, initial set of fixed cell indices \mathcal{F}

Output: Optimized unit cell vertices $\{\mathbf{v}_j^{(k)*}\}_{j=1}^8$ for $k = 1, \dots, N$

Solve Eq. (S12) to obtain initial vertex positions \mathcal{V}_0 ;

Determine search order $\mathcal{S} = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_N]$ according to the prioritization rules;

for $i = 1$ **to** N **do**

- Retrieve nearest-neighbor configuration from dataset:
- $c^* \leftarrow \arg \min_{1 \leq c \leq |\mathcal{D}|} \sum_{j=1}^8 \|\mathbf{v}_j^{(s_i)} - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_j^{(c)}\|^2$;
- Align $\mathcal{C}^{(c^*)}$ to the current cell location via rotation about the known vertex axis;
- Substitute aligned configuration: $\mathbf{v}_j^{(s_i)} \leftarrow \hat{\mathbf{v}}_j^{(c^*)}$ for $j = 1, \dots, 8$;
- Update fixed cell set: $\mathcal{F} \leftarrow \mathcal{F} \cup \{s_i\}$;
- Re-solve Eq. (S12) to obtain updated \mathcal{V} ;

return $\mathbf{v}_j^{(k)*} \leftarrow \mathbf{v}_j^{(k)}$ for $k = 1, \dots, N, j = 1, \dots, 8$;

Fig. S3a illustrates the execution of the AS algorithm. At each step, the current cell is matched against the dataset using its known fixed vertices to retrieve the nearest-neighbor configuration. Upon substitution, all vertices of the updated cell are added to the fixed set, and the next cell is selected as the neighbor with the greatest number of already-fixed vertices. A comparison of dissimilarity scores before and after the AS update (Figs. S3b–c) shows a marked reduction in overall dissimilarity, confirming that the retrieved configurations are more consistent with the dataset and thus more reliably reconstructed during microscale inverse design.

3.2 Conditional diffusion model

This section introduces the conditional diffusion model (cDM) as the second microscale inverse design method, covering its theoretical foundation, model architecture, conditioning strategy, and training details.

Figure S3: Adjustable search (AS) method. **a.** Illustration of the AS procedure. **b and c.** Dissimilarity scores before (b) and after (c) AS for a curved beam example.

3.2.1 Fundamentals of the denoising diffusion probabilistic model (DDPM)

The denoising diffusion probabilistic model (DDPM) [5] defines a forward process that progressively corrupts clean design parameters \mathbf{x}_0 into pure Gaussian noise \mathbf{x}_T , and a reverse process in which a deep neural network learns to reconstruct the original design from noise. In the forward process, Gaussian noise $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$ is added to \mathbf{x}_0 according to a predefined noise schedule $\{\beta_t \in (0, 1)\}_{t=1}^T$, forming a Markov chain:

$$q(\mathbf{x}_{1:T}|\mathbf{x}_0) = \prod_{t=1}^T q(\mathbf{x}_t|\mathbf{x}_{t-1}), \quad q(\mathbf{x}_t|\mathbf{x}_{t-1}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_t; \sqrt{\alpha_t} \mathbf{x}_{t-1}, (1 - \alpha_t)\mathbf{I}), \quad (\text{S18})$$

where $\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{i=1}^t (1 - \beta_i)$, which allows sampling at arbitrary timesteps via:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{x}_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \epsilon. \quad (\text{S19})$$

The reverse process begins by sampling $\mathbf{x}_T \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$ and iteratively samples from $p(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}|\mathbf{x}_t)$ until \mathbf{x}_0 is reconstructed. This distribution is parameterized by a neural network:

$$p_\phi(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}|\mathbf{x}_t) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}; \boldsymbol{\mu}_\phi(\mathbf{x}_t, t), \sigma_t^2 \mathbf{I}), \quad (\text{S20})$$

where ϕ denotes the network parameters and the variance is fixed as:

$$\sigma_t^2 = \frac{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \beta_t. \quad (\text{S21})$$

Following [5], the network is trained by directly predicting the added noise rather than maximizing the evidence lower bound (ELBO):

$$\mathcal{L}(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}), \mathbf{x}_0, t \sim \text{Unif}(1, T)} \left[\|\epsilon - \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_\phi(\mathbf{x}_t, t)\|^2 \right]. \quad (\text{S22})$$

3.2.2 Conditional encoding

Since the task requires generating unit cell designs conditioned on the target deformed configuration θ , a conditional diffusion model is employed:

$$q_\phi(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}|\mathbf{x}_t, \theta) = \mathcal{N}\left(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}; \mu_\phi(\mathbf{x}_t, t, \theta), \sigma_t^2 \mathbf{I}\right). \tag{S23}$$

Following [6], the condition θ is injected via cross-attention at multiple scales of the U-Net. At each downsampling block, the feature map is fused with a cross-attention output computed from θ , then processed by residual and attention layers before downsampling. The same conditioning is applied at the bottleneck and at each upsampling block after skip concatenation, ensuring that condition information is continuously re-incorporated throughout both the compression and reconstruction stages.

3.2.3 Model architecture and training details

The noisy input is first projected by a 7×1 stem convolution. The diffusion timestep is encoded via a sinusoidal embedding [7] followed by a two-layer MLP, which modulates all ResNet [8] blocks through scale-shift conditioning. The encoder comprises four stages with channel progression $d \rightarrow 2d \rightarrow 4d \rightarrow 8d$ [9], each applying cross-attention with θ , two time-conditioned ResNet blocks, linear attention, and downsampling. The bottleneck consists of cross-attention, a ResNet block, full self-attention, and a second ResNet block. The decoder mirrors the encoder with skip connections. The decoder output is fused with the stem residual, passed through a final ResNet block, and projected by a 1×1 convolution to produce the diffusion target. Full hyperparameters are listed in Table S2.

During training, automatic mixed precision (AMP, fp16), gradient clipping (maximum norm = 1.0), and exponential moving average (EMA, decay = 0.995) are employed to stabilize optimization. The model is trained on a Linux workstation using Python 3.11.14 and PyTorch 2.8.0 with CUDA and cuDNN support, equipped with one NVIDIA RTX A4000 GPU (16 GB) and an Intel Xeon w5-3423 CPU (12 cores). The dataset of 60,000 samples is split into training and test sets at an 8:2 ratio, and the model is trained for 10,000 epochs, with the full training process completing in approximately one hour.

Table S2: Hyperparameters of the conditional diffusion model.

Hyperparameter	Value
ResNet blocks per downsampling stage	2
ResNet blocks per upsampling stage	2
Residual block normalization	RMS Normalization
Activation function	SiLU
Time embedding	Sinusoidal positional embedding + 2-layer MLP
Conditional embedding	Linear projection + 4 conditional residual MLP blocks
Attention head dimension	32
Number of attention heads	4
Sequence resolutions	$8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$
Feature dimension	$d \rightarrow 2d \rightarrow 4d \rightarrow 8d$
Initial feature dimension	$d = 4$

Figure S4: Comparison of the target deformation configurations sampled from the test set and the simulated configurations of generated unit cells. The blue dashed line presents the target configurations, while the filled green shapes present the simulated configurations.

3.2.4 Model performance

To evaluate the cDM, we randomly selected 1,000 samples from the test set. For each sample, the target response configuration θ and randomly sampled initial noise were fed into the model to generate candidate infill designs. The generated parameters were clipped to the predefined feasible design ranges to ensure geometric validity, and FEA was performed on the resulting structures to obtain their deformation responses. We computed the coefficient of determination R^2 between the simulated responses and the target configurations, achieving an average R^2 of 0.87. Fig. S4 visualizes 64 randomly selected samples, showing that the majority of generated designs closely match their target configurations, with only a small number exhibiting noticeable deviations. Overall, the model achieves sufficient accuracy for the microscale inverse design stage.

4 Time complexity analysis

To compare the computational efficiency of the SAM framework with FEM-based optimization methods, we conduct a time-complexity analysis for the design of a two-dimensional metamaterial comprising an $N \times N$ array of unit cells. Topology optimization (TO) is selected as the representative baseline, as it is generally more computationally efficient than alternative optimization approaches such as genetic algorithms.

For TO, the number of iterations required for convergence is problem-dependent; we denote this as k . The computational domain is discretized using quadrilateral finite elements, with each unit cell meshed using an $m \times m$ finite element grid.

For the weakly coupled thermomechanical problem considered here, the dominant computational cost at each iteration arises from solving the finite element system. Employing a direct solver, the complexity of each solve scales as $O(nw^2)$ [10], where n denotes the number of nodes and w is the bandwidth of the global stiffness matrix. For the uniform grid considered here, the total number of nodes is $n = (mN + 1)^2$, and the bandwidth is $w = 2(mN + 1)$.

The overall computational complexity of TO over k iterations, therefore, scales as

$$O\left(2k(mN + 1)(mN + 1)^2\right) \approx O(km^3N^3), \quad (\text{S24})$$

which scales cubically with the problem size.

For the SAM framework, no FEM simulation is required, and the computational complexity decomposes into two stages. In the macroscale solving stage, the time complexity of Laplacian mesh editing scales quadratically with the number of vertices [11], i.e.,

$$O(N^2), \quad (\text{S25})$$

since the number of vertices in the mesh is proportional to N^2 .

In the microscale design stage, the cDM-based approach is taken as a representative example. Assuming each batch accommodates at most C samples and that generating a single sample incurs a complexity of $O(T C_{\text{model}})$, where T denotes the number of diffusion steps and C_{model} represents the cost of a single U-Net forward pass, the overall complexity of the microscale design stage is given by

$$O\left(\left\lceil \frac{(2N + 1)^2}{C} \right\rceil T C_{\text{model}}\right). \quad (\text{S26})$$

Under fixed batch size and diffusion settings, the overall time complexity combining both stages is

$$O(N^2) + O\left(\left\lceil \frac{(2N + 1)^2}{C} \right\rceil T C_{\text{model}}\right) \approx O(N^2). \quad (\text{S27})$$

This approximation holds when T and C_{model} are sufficiently small relative to N , which is satisfied in practice since the number of diffusion steps and the U-Net complexity are fixed constants independent of the structural resolution. Denoting the total number of unit cells as $N_c = N^2$, the design time of the cDM-based SAM therefore scales as $O(N_c)$.

5 Comparison of domain discretization methods

The decomposition strategy adopted in this work treats a closed-loop linkage composed of multiple bars as the minimal design unit. Compared with the conventional approach that discretizes the design domain into bar-based structures connected by ideal hinges [12, 13], we demonstrate, using a simple example, why SAM uses unit-level discretization.

5.1 Problem setup

Given a rectangular material domain of length 2 mm and width 1 mm as shown in Fig. S5, with its left boundary fixed, we design the embedded active material using either bars or unit cells as the basic design elements, such that the upper-right corner undergoes a downward displacement of $d = 0.2$ mm. We consider a simple solution where this domain is discretized into two equal squares.

Figure S5: A simple shape-morphing problem

The solution of a bar-based design can be manually derived using nine bars, as shown in Fig. S6, where the gray outer bars are passive members, and the blue bars are active members made of the same material. Under this setup, the initial length of each passive bar is $L_p = 1$ mm, while the initial length of each active bar is $L_a = 1.414$ mm. We can solve this simple bar-based design problem analytically. Assuming that the passive material does not deform and that all active members undergo the same strain, the deformed angle β is given by

$$\beta^* = \frac{\pi}{2} + \arcsin\left(\frac{d}{2}\right) = 1.670963. \quad (\text{S28})$$

Accordingly, the deformed length of the blue bars becomes

$$L_a^* = 2L_a \sin\left(\frac{\beta^*}{2}\right) = 1.4832. \quad (\text{S29})$$

The resulting strain in each active bar is therefore

$$\epsilon = \frac{L_a^* - L_a}{L_a} = 0.0488. \quad (\text{S30})$$

To realize this target strain through thermal expansion, we set the coefficient of thermal expansion of the active material to 4.88×10^{-4} and apply a temperature increase of 100°C , followed by a finite element simulation.

For the unit-cell-based discretization, we adopt the same setup as in the previously described AS-based SAM for inverse design.

5.2 Results of SAM and bar-based framework

As shown in Fig. S6, finite element simulations indicate that the deformation error of the bar-based design reaches 39.67% compared to the theoretically achievable configuration, whereas the error of the AS-based SAM design is only 7.16%. This discrepancy arises because the bar-based design neglects the interactions between adjacent bars and considers only axial deformation. In practice, this simplification introduces significant errors. Moreover, as the number of bars increases, the likelihood of failure also grows, as evidenced by the buckling observed in some of the structures presented in [13]. In contrast, the unit-cell-based design implicitly incorporates the interactions among structural elements through the dataset of unit-cell configurations. As a result, when assembled, it is able to achieve more accurate and stable deformation behavior.

5.3 Deformation mode ambiguity in bar-based design frameworks

Another fundamental limitation of bar-based design frameworks is the inherent ambiguity in their deformation modes. Consider the two-bar system shown in Fig. S6c, where both ends A and C are fixed, and the design intent is to displace the intermediate node B upward (red path). However, the same bar design is equally compatible with a downward displacement of B (green path), since axial deformation alone carries no directional information. As a result, the realized deformation mode depends on the assembly configuration rather than the design itself, introducing an irresolvable ambiguity. The unit cell-based approach adopted in the SAM framework eliminates this ambiguity by assigning each cell a unique, directionally encoded deformation mode, ensuring that the intended deformation is unambiguously realized upon assembly.

Figure S6: Comparison of bar-based and cell-based discretizations. **a**, The simulation results of bar-based element design. **b**, The simulation results of unit cell-based element design (using AS-based SAM). **c**, The demonstration of deformation mode ambiguity in bar-based design frameworks.

6 More examples

This section presents additional shape-morphing examples to further demonstrate the generality of the SAM framework. Nine pairs of initial and target airfoil shapes were selected from the dataset [14, 15] and designed using the cDM-based SAM framework, with FEA results shown in Fig. S7 and quantitative metrics summarized in Table S3. A design is considered successful when the mean relative error satisfies $MRE < 35\%$. Cases a, b, c, e, f, and h satisfy the success criterion, whereas cases d, g, and i exhibit larger errors. achievable range.

Figure S7: More airfoil shape matching examples. The green dots indicate the deformed positions, and the blue curves indicate the target positions.

Table S3: Quantitative error statistics of all examples.

Case	N_{cells}	$N_{handles}$	MAE	R^2	L_c	MRE	Success
Fig. S6a	2524	31	1.9798	0.9786	7.99	24.78%	✓
Fig. S6b	3408	36	2.3326	0.9837	7.50	31.10%	✓
Fig. S6c	4104	36	0.9125	0.9971	5.08	17.96%	✓
Fig. S6d	3588	38	6.5312	0.8915	6.05	108.02%	✗
Fig. S6e	4267	31	4.2400	0.9609	13.51	31.99%	✓
Fig. S6f	3294	33	1.9378	0.9816	7.02	27.60%	✓
Fig. S6g	4484	42	7.6888	0.8327	9.88	77.79%	✗
Fig. S6h	3215	38	1.5138	0.9883	4.83	31.37%	✓
Fig. S6i	1354	23	4.5671	0.2236	9.16	49.86%	✗

Revisiting the macroscale solutions for cases d, g, and i (Fig. S8) clarifies the sources of error in each case. In cases d and g (Figs. S8a–b), the fixed cells at the leading edge are assigned large deformations by the ConLME. Since all degrees of freedom of the fixed cell are constrained during FEA, this induces a rigid-body rotation of the assembled structure, causing the final shape to deviate from the target. In case i, the target airfoil is geometrically too narrow to be physically realized, forcing a small number of unit cells into extreme and overlapping configurations. This localized failure propagates to the global deformation, resulting in large errors.

Figure S8: The dissimilarity score distribution on the macroscale solution of cases d (a), g (b), and i (c).

7 Proof of volume reduction

We provide the proof of the volume reduction properties of SAM. To obtain the theoretical area of the deformed metamaterial, we consider an ideal case with just the undetermined mechanism, as shown in Fig. S9a. Each bar has a length of l . So the initial area for n square cells is,

$$S_0 = 4nl^2. \quad (\text{S31})$$

Once the mechanism deformed as shown in Fig. S9b, the shape of the unit cell will become irregular. By connecting the corner vertices of each cell in sequence, a set of virtual boundaries is formed, which enclose the shaded region Ω shown in Fig. S9b. Apparently, the length of an arbitrary virtual edge of one unit cell should be smaller than the length of a square in the original configuration, e.g., $l_i < 2l$. Since the boundaries are negligible when the number of unit cells increases, we could just consider the area of region Ω . In this case, the area of the deformed region can be computed by summing the areas of individual cells, each defined by the regions enclosed by their corner points. Thus, the total area of the arbitrary region could be calculated by,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{S} &= \sum_{i=1}^n (S_1^i + S_2^i) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{2} l_1^i l_2^i \sin \theta_1^i + \frac{1}{2} l_3^i l_4^i \sin \theta_2^i \right) \\ &\leq \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{2} 4l^2 (\sin \theta_1^i + \sin \theta_2^i) \\ &\leq \sum_{i=1}^n 4l^2 = 4nl^2 = S_0. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S32})$$

Thus, the total area only reduces after deformation.

Figure S9: Proof of compactness. a. The initial mesh. **b.** The deformed mesh

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